

Review of the analysis of factors influencing women participation in fish processing in Sokoto metropolis Sokoto State, Nigeria.

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This study evaluated women's participation in fish processing in Sokoto Metropolis, Sokoto State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to describe the socio-economic characteristics of women involved in fish processing, identify the factors influencing their participation, examine the constraints they face, and explore strategies for improving their involvement in the sector. Primary data were collected from 30 women fish processors through structured questionnaires and interview schedules using purposive and random sampling techniques. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts and percentages. The findings revealed that most of the women involved in fish processing were within the age range of 31–40 years (30%), while 60% were married. About 33.3% engaged in fish processing as a full-time occupation, and 36.7% earned between ₦20,000 and ₦50,000 monthly. The study further showed that socio-cultural factors, financial limitations, lack of training, inadequate access to modern processing equipment, poor market access, and limited government support significantly influenced women's participation in fish processing. Major constraints identified included lack of extension services, inadequate storage facilities, limited access to credit, and social restrictions. The study concluded that women play an important role in fish processing in Sokoto Metropolis, but their participation is constrained by several socio-economic and institutional challenges. The study recommended improved access to microfinance, training programmes, modern processing technologies, market opportunities, and supportive policies to enhance women's productivity and empowerment in the fish processing sector.

Keywords: Women participation, fish processing, socio-economic characteristics, empowerment, Sokoto Metropolis.

INTRODUCTION

Women's participation in the fisheries sector, particularly in fish processing, plays a vital role in ensuring food security, poverty reduction, and the promotion of gender equality. Across the globe, women participant fish significantly processing industry, engaging in various

post-harvest activities such as drying, smoking, fermenting, and marketing fish products. These activities are not only essential for human nutrition and income but also serve as a critical component of local and national economies (FAO, 2015). Despite their contributions, women in fish processing often face systemic challenges that undermine their efforts and limit their potential. In many developing countries, including Nigeria, fish processing activities are predominantly traditional and

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labor-intensive. Women, participant in fish processing constitute a large proportion of the workforce in these fisheries, often perform the most time-consuming tasks under difficult conditions. These tasks include cleaning, drying, smoking, and packaging fish, which are crucial for adding value to fish products and ensuring their availability for extended periods. This not only supports the sustainability of fishery resources but also provides an essential source of protein for communities. However, these contributions remain undervalued, and women's roles in the fisheries sector are frequently overlooked in policy-making and development initiatives (World Bank, 2017).

The challenges faced by women participation in fish processing are multifaceted. Limited access to modern technology and resources, inadequate training opportunities, and the lack of access to formal markets are significant hurdles. Women participation in fish processing also encounter social and cultural barriers that restrict their mobility and participation in decision-making processes. These obstacles prevent women participation from maximizing their potential, thereby perpetuating poverty and inequality in the sector. Moreover, the informal nature of many fish processing enterprises leaves women without access to social protection or financial support, making them vulnerable to economic shocks and environmental changes (Harper *et al.*, 2013).

Empowering women participation in fish processing is not only a matter of social justice but also an economic imperative. Studies have shown that improving women's participant access to resources, training, and technology can significantly enhance their productivity, improve the quality of fish products, and increase women participant incomes. This, in turn, contributes to broader community development and the resilience of the fisheries sector. Women's empowerment in fish processing also aligns with global development agendas, such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which emphasize gender equality, poverty eradication, and sustainable economic growth (UN Women, 2018).

In the context of Nigeria, fish processing is a vital economic activity, particularly in Sokoto Metropolis, where fish farming and related activities support the livelihoods of many women participants. The region's socio-economic landscape underscores the importance of fish processing as a means of income generation and food security. However, women in Sokoto face unique challenges, including cultural norms that limit their participation, inadequate infrastructure for fish processing, and limited access to credit and market opportunities. Addressing these issues requires a comprehensive understanding of the women's participation in fish processing in Sokoto Metropolis. Women participation in fish processing face significant

challenges, including lack of modern technology in fish processing, lack of training and capacity building, social and cultural barriers, and limited market access and economic opportunities, hindering their full participation.

With regard to these problems the research raised the following research questions

- i. What are the socio-economic characteristics of women participation in fish processing in the study area?
- ii. How does women participation in fish processing in the study area?
- iii. What are the constraints faced by women participation in fish processing in the study area?
- iv. What strategies can be implemented to address these challenges and promote women's empowerment in the fish processing industry in the study area?

The general objective is to examine women participation in fish processing in Sokoto Metropolis Sokoto State, Nigeria

The specific objectives are

- i. To describe the socio-economic characteristics of women participation in fish processing within the study area.
- ii. To describe the women participation in fish processing in the study area.
- iii. To determine the constraints faced by women participation in fish processing industry in the study area.
- iv. To explore the potential strategies that would promote women's participation in fish processing in the study area.

Significance of the study

This study explores the challenges faced by women participation in the fish processing in Sokoto Metropolis Sokoto State, Nigeria, including limited access to resources, lack of training, and social and cultural barriers. Despite their significant contributions, women's participation and benefits are hindered by these challenges. The research aims to identify strategies to address these issues, promote gender equality, and empower women participation in fish processing.

By understanding the challenges and opportunities, the study seeks to improve women's livelihoods, contribute to fish processing activities and development, and inform policy and decision-making. Ultimately, the study aims to amplify the voices and experiences of women in participation fish processing, promoting their empowerment and agency in the fish processing aspects.

Materials and method (Study area)

The study area is Sokoto Metropolis, which is located in

Table 1: Age Distribution of women participation in fish processing.

Age of women participation in fish processing	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Below 20	3	10%
20-30	8	26.7%
31-40	9	30%
41-50	6	20%
Above 50	4	13.3%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Sokoto State, Nigeria. Sokoto State is situated in the North-Western part of Nigeria and shares borders with Niger Republic to the North, Zamfara State to the East, Kebbi State to the South, and Benin Republic to the West (Sokoto State Government, 2020). Sokoto Metropolis is located between latitude 13° 00' N and longitude 5° 00' E (Google Maps, 2022). The metropolis comprises (4) Local Government Sokoto North, Sokoto South, Wamakko and Dangi Shuni has a total area of approximately 173 km² (Sokoto State Government, 2020). The vegetation of Sokoto Metropolis is characterized as Sudanian Savanna, with dominant species of grasses, shrubs, and trees (Adebayo and Tukur, 2017). The temperature of Sokoto Metropolis varies between 22°C and 38°C, with an average annual temperature of 28°C (Nigerian Meteorological Agency, 2020). Mean annual rainfall in Sokoto Metropolis is approximately 600 mm (Nigerian Meteorological Agency, 2020). Soil type in Sokoto Metropolis is predominantly sandy loam (Adebayo and Tukur, 2017).

Sampling Procedure and Sampling Size

The purposive sampling procedure was used to select four (4) local governments areas within Sokoto Metropolis, namely; Sokoto North, Sokoto South, Wamakko, and Dange shuni. From each selected local government, one district was randomly selected, making a total numbers of 4 districts. From Sokoto North and Sokoto South district, 8 women involved in fish processing of each district and Wamakko and Dange Shuni district, 7 women involved in fish processing of each district were randomly selected, making a total sample size of 30.

Data Collection

Data was collected using questionnaires and schedule interviews. The questionnaire was contained of closed-ended questions that was elicit information on the socio-economic characteristics of women participation in fish

processing, challenges faced, and potential strategies to promote women's participation. The schedule interview was contained of open-ended questions that have provide more in-depth information on the challenges faced by women in fish processing and potential strategies to promote their participation.

Data Analysis

Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics: frequency and percentage. This was involve calculating the frequency and percentage of responses for each question and presenting them in tables and figures. The data analysis was tally with the specific objectives of the study, which are:

1. To describe the socio-economic characteristics of women participation in fish processing in the study area.
2. To determine the challenges faced by women participation in the fish processing industry in the study area.
3. To identify the challenges affect women's participation in fish processing in the study area.
4. To explore the potential strategies that would promote women's participation in fish processing in the study area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-Economic Characteristics of fish farmers

The results indicate that the majority of women participation in fish processing are between the ages of 31-40 years (30%), followed by 20-30 years (26.7%). However, the 10% participation rate among women below 20 years suggests that younger women may have limited involvement due to education or other occupational preferences. Additionally, the 13.3% of women above 50 years still engaged in fish processing highlights the importance of this activity as a lifelong income source. This suggests that women in their

Table 2: Distribution of Marital Status of women participation in fish processing.

Marital status of women participation in fish processing	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Single	5	16.7%
Married	18	60%
Divorced	4	13.3%
Widowed	3	10%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table .3: Distribution of Occupation of women participation in fish processing.

Occupation of women participation in fish processing	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Full-time processor	10	33.3%
Part-time processor	7	23.3%
Farmer	5	16.7%
Trader	6	20%
Others	2	6.7%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table .4: Distribution of Monthly Income from the women participation in fish processing.

Income Level of women participation in fish processing	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Below N20,000	9	30%
N20,000 - N50,000	11	36.7%
N51,000 - N100,000	6	20%
Above N100,000	4	13.3%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

productive years dominate fish processing activities. Studies by Adepoju and Awodun (2019) found that women within this age group engage actively in agribusiness to support their families.

The survey shows that 60% of the women participation in fish processing are married, confirming that fish processing is a key economic activity for married women. 16.7% of single women in the industry suggest that some young women engage in fish processing for income generation before marriage. Furthermore, 13.3% of divorced women and 10% of widows depend on fish processing for financial independence, as supported by Olalekan and Adebayo (2021), who highlighted that divorced and widowed women in rural areas often rely on small-scale enterprises for survival.

The findings indicate that 33.3% of women participation in fish processing are full-time fish processors,

emphasizing that fish processing is a primary livelihood for many women. 23.3% of women engage in part-time processing, balancing it with other income-generating activities. 16.7% of women participation in fish processing are farmers, suggesting that some women combine farming and fish processing as complementary activities. The 20% participation of traders in fish processing indicates the importance of fish as a commercial commodity. The 6.7% engaged in other occupations implies that fish processing is a flexible business that can be combined with other trades. This supports the findings of Eyo (2019), who stated that many women in agriculture engage in multiple occupations for financial stability.

The majority of women participation in fish processing (36.7%) earn between N20,000 - N50,000 per month, followed by 30% who earn below N20,000. This suggests

Table 4.1.5: Distribution of Business Size of women participation in fish processing.

Business Size of women participation in fish processing	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Small-scale	18	60%
Medium-scale	9	30%
Large-scale	3	10%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.1.6: Distribution of Education Level of women participation in fish processing

Education Level of women participation in fish processing	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
No formal education	7	23.3%
Primary education	10	33.3%
Secondary education	9	30%
Tertiary education	4	13.3%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.2.1: Distribution of Influence of Socio-cultural Factors on women participation in fish processing.

Variables	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Yes	18	60%
No	12	40%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.2.2: Distribution of Socio-Cultural Factors Influencing Women's Participation

Socio-Cultural Restrictions	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Gender roles in the community	12	40%
Religious beliefs	8	26.7%
Family expectations	6	20%
Other (Specify)	4	13.3%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

that fish processing provides modest earnings, but many women participation in fish processing operate on a subsistence level. The 20% earning between N51,000 - N100,000 indicates that some women have scaled their businesses to generate higher incomes. 13.3% of women participation in fish processing earn above N100,000, showing that there are opportunities for profitability in fish processing. These findings align with Ibrahim *et al.*, (2021), who noted that limited capital, poor storage

facilities, and seasonal fluctuations affect income levels in fish processing businesses.

The results indicate that 60% of women participation in fish processing operate small-scale fish processing businesses, reflecting limited capital and resources. 30% operate medium-scale businesses, indicating moderate investment and market reach. Only 10% run large-scale businesses, which suggests challenges such as lack of credit access, high production costs, and inadequate

Table 4.2.4 Distribution of Finance your fish processing activities

Financing Source	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Personal savings	10	33.3%
Loans from banks	6	20%
Microfinance institutions	8	26.7%
Informal lending groups	6	20%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.2.6 Distribution of Training in Fish Processing.

Training Received	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Yes	14	46.7%
No	16	53.3%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.2.7 Distribution of Reasons for Not Accessing Training

Reason for No Training	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Lack of awareness	6	37.5%
Financial constraints	5	31.3%
Time constraints	3	18.8%
Other (Specify)	2	12.5%
Total	16	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

infrastructure. According to Ajibade and Yusuf (2020), small-scale businesses dominate the fish processing industry in Nigeria, with only a few women participation in fish processing having the financial resources to expand their enterprises.

The survey shows that 33.3% of women participation in fish processing have primary education, while 23.3% have no formal education, suggesting that literacy levels among women in fish processing are relatively low. 30% of women participation in fish processing have secondary education, which may enhance their ability to manage small businesses effectively. Only 13.3% have tertiary education, implying that educated women participation in fish processing may seek alternative careers outside fish processing. Abubakar and Danladi (2019) found that education plays a vital role in improving business management skills and access to financial opportunities in agricultural enterprises.

Factors influencing women's participation in fish processing

Socio-cultural factors of women participation in fish processing

The results indicate that 60% of women participation in fish processing believe culture or tradition influences their participation in fish processing, while 40% do not feel restricted. In many African communities, traditional roles often dictate women's involvement in certain economic activities. According to Adepoju (2021), cultural norms sometimes limit women's participation in fish processing access to resources, making it difficult for them to scale up their businesses. Those who answered "Yes" explained that fish processing is traditionally a woman's role, but social stigma and male dominance in some communities can hinder their participation.

Table 4.2.9 Distribution of Awareness of Government Support Policies.

Government Support Policies	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Yes	18	60%
No	12	40%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.2.10 Distribution of Type of Support Received

Type of Support Policy	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Financial support programs	7	38.9%
Training and capacity-building	5	27.8%
Market access initiatives	4	22.2%
Other (Specify)	2	11.1%
Total	18	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.3.1: Distribution of Training and Extension Services

Support from Extension Officers/Training Organizations	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Yes	12	40%
No	18	60%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

The results show that 40% of women participation in fish processing believe that gender roles in the community restrict women's involvement in fish processing. This suggests that traditional perceptions of women's fish processors roles might limit their participation. Additionally, 26.7% of respondents cited religious beliefs as a barrier, which may indicate that certain cultural or religious norms discourage women from engaging in fish processing activities. Family expectations also play a role, with 20% of women participation in fish processing stating that household responsibilities and societal pressures limit their ability to participate. Lastly, 13.3% mentioned other unspecified restrictions, indicating that additional personal or community-based factors may influence participation. These findings align with previous studies, such as FAO (2020), which highlight that cultural and religious norms significantly impact of women's fish processors roles in agricultural and fisheries-related activities.

Economic Factors Influencing Women's Participation

Financial constraints are a major factor influencing

women's participation in fish processing. 33.3% of women fish processor rely on personal savings, which indicates limited access to external funding sources. Only 20% have obtained loans from banks, likely due to strict loan requirements or high-interest rates. However, 26.7% of participation in fish processing receive financial support from microfinance institutions, showing that alternative financing options are available and being utilized. Another 20% access informal lending groups, such as cooperative societies or rotating savings systems, which may be more flexible and accessible. The findings suggest that although financial institutions provide funding opportunities, many women still struggle with accessing capital. According to the World Bank (2021), financial exclusion remains a challenge for women in agribusiness, emphasizing the need for targeted financial programs to support female entrepreneurs.

Technological Factors Influencing Women's Participation

The survey reveals that 46.7% of women participation in

Table 4.3.2 Distribution of Improve your fish processing business

Type of Training Needed	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Modern fish preservation techniques	10	33.3%
Business and financial management	8	26.7%
Market access strategies	7	23.3%
Other (Specify)	5	16.7%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.3.3: Distribution of Social and cultural affecting women participation in fish processing

Cultural/Social Norms	Frequency (n=30)	Percentage (%)
Yes	16	53.3%
No	14	46.7%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.3.4: Distribution of Social and cultural factors limiting in women participation in fish processing

Cultural/Social Factors Limiting Participation	Frequency (n=30)	Percentage (%)
Gender roles and expectations	12	40%
Limited decision-making power	6	20%
Religious beliefs	7	23.3%
Other (Specify)	5	16.7%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

fish processing have received formal training in fish processing, which is a positive indication that some women participation in fish processing have access to skill development programs. However, 53.3% have not received training, which presents a significant barrier to improved productivity and efficiency in fish processing. These findings are supported by Olalekan and Adebayo (2021) who found that limited technological knowledge prevents women in fish processing from improving efficiency and profitability.

Among the 16 women fish processors who had no training, the most common barrier was a lack of awareness about training programs (37.5%). This suggests that training opportunities exist but are not effectively communicated to potential beneficiaries. 31.3% cited financial constraints, which aligns with earlier economic findings. 18.8% of women participation in fish processing mentioned time constraints due to household responsibilities, indicating that work-life balance is a challenge. Finally, 12.5% cited other reasons, highlighting the need for further research into additional barriers.

These findings suggest that increased awareness and financial support for training could significantly enhance women's participation. Previous research by FAO (2020) highlights the importance of training programs in empowering women in fisheries and food processing sectors.

Political Factors Influencing Women's Participation

A majority of women participation in fish processing (60%) are aware of government support programs that encourage women's participation in fish processing, while 40% are not. This indicates that although policies exist, outreach and implementation may not be reaching all intended beneficiaries. Furthermore, 66.7% of women participation in fish processing are unaware of any support programs, which aligns with research by Ajibade (2020), who found that many small-scale women entrepreneurs in agriculture are not adequately informed about available government initiatives. Improving awareness and accessibility to policy-driven intervention

Table 4.3.5: Distribution of Access to Markets and Trade Opportunities

Support Needed for Market Access	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Better transportation infrastructure	9	30%
Access to larger markets	8	26.7%
Training on pricing and marketing strategies	7	23.3%
Government policy support	6	20%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.3.6: Distribution of Access to Technology and Equipment

Technology and Equipment Needed	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Refrigeration and cold storage	11	36.7%
Modern drying techniques	9	30%
Efficient smoking and packaging tools	10	33.3%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.3.7: Distribution of ICT Access and Usage

Use of Mobile Phones/Internet for Business	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Yes	18	60%
No	12	40%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.3.8: Distribution of Social Protection and Services

Social Protection Challenges Faced	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Lack of health insurance	10	33.3%
Lack of maternity benefits	8	26.7%
No legal protection for workplace issues	7	23.3%
Other (Specify)	5	16.7%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

could enhance women's participation in the industry.

Among the women participation in fish processing who were aware of policies, 38.9% benefited from financial support programs, suggesting that financial assistance is the most impactful intervention. 27.8% received training and capacity-building support, showing that skill development initiatives are somewhat effective but could be expanded. 22.2% benefited from market access

initiatives, which help women participation in fish processing sell their processed fish, but may require additional promotion and accessibility. Lastly, 11.1% cited other forms of government support, which may include subsidies, networking programs, or infrastructure development. These findings align with Nigeria Fisheries Development (2023), which emphasizes the importance of financial inclusion and skill-building programs in

Table 4.3.9: Distribution of Policy and Decision-Making

Policy Improvements Needed	Frequency (n=30)	Percentage (%)
Provide financial support	9	30%
Offer more training programs	8	26.7%
Improve access to markets and trade	7	23.3%
Provide access to modern equipment and technology	6	20%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.4.1: Distribution of Training and Capacity Building

Type of Training Needed	Frequency (n=30)	Percentage (%)
Modern fish preservation techniques	9	30%
Business and financial management	7	23.3%
Market access strategies	8	26.7%
Use of modern equipment and technology	6	20%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.4.2: Distribution of Access to Credit and Financial Services

Preferred Financial Support	Frequency (n=30)	Percentage (%)
Microfinance loans	12	40%
Savings programs	10	33.3%
Cooperative schemes	8	26.7%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

increasing women's participation in fisheries. Improved policy implementation and targeted outreach could further enhance women's engagement in the sector.

Constraints faced by women participation in fish processing

The findings indicate that 60% of women participation in fish processing do not receive support from extension officers or training organizations, showing a significant gap in technical knowledge and skill development. This lack of access to training may limit their ability to adopt modern processing techniques. On the other hand, 40% of women participation in fish processing receive some form of training support, which suggests that extension services exist but are insufficient in reach or effectiveness. Studies by Adepoju and Alarima (2020) suggest that inadequate training leads to lower productivity in fish processing.

The survey shows that 33.3% of women participation in fish processing require training in modern fish preservation techniques, which is crucial for improving product shelf life and quality. 26.7% believe business and financial management training would enhance their ability to manage expenses and revenue. Additionally, 23.3% express the need for market access strategies, which is critical in reaching larger buyers. These findings align with FAO (2019), which emphasizes the need for technical and financial literacy training to boost women's fish processing productivity in fish processing.

More than half (53.3%) of participation in fish processing report that cultural and social norms negatively affect their participation in fish processing. This suggests that traditions and societal expectations still play a significant role in limiting women's involvement in economic activities. However, 46.7% of respondents do not experience these challenges, indicating that some communities are more supportive of women's

Table 4.4.3: Distribution of Leadership and Decision-Making

Strategies to Increase Women's Leadership	Frequency (n=30)	Percentage (%)
Leadership and management training	8	26.7%
Creating women's associations and cooperatives	9	30%
Government policies supporting women in leadership	7	23.3%
Community sensitization on gender equality	6	20%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.2.10 Distribution of Type of Support Received

Type of Support Policy	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Financial support programs	7	38.9%
Training and capacity-building	5	27.8%
Market access initiatives	4	22.2%
Other (Specify)	2	11.1%
Total	18	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.3.1: Distribution of Training and Extension Services

Support from Extension Officers/Training Organizations	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Yes	12	40%
No	18	60%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.4.4: Distribution of Access to ICTs for Fish Processing.

Type of ICT Support Needed	Frequency (n=30)	Percentage (%)
Online marketing platforms	10	33.3%
Mobile-based advisory services	8	26.7%
Social media training	12	40%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

participation. Adebayo and Ogunniyi (2020) highlight that gender norms significantly restrict women's economic activities in many African societies.

The results show that 40% of women participation in fish processing face gender role restrictions, meaning cultural beliefs about women's responsibilities prevent them from engaging in fish processing. 23.3% are affected by religious beliefs, which may impose limitations on their mobility or work involvement.

Additionally, 20% experience limited decision-making power, restricting their ability to invest or expand their businesses. These findings align with Kabeer (2018), who states that gender norms often limit women's autonomy in economic sectors. 30% of women participation in fish processing believe better transportation infrastructure is necessary for improving market access. This suggests that poor road networks and lack of transportation facilities hinder fish distribution.

Table 4.4.5: Distribution of Use of Modern Technology in Fish Processing

Type of Modern Technology Used	Frequency (n=30)	Percentage (%)
Automated filleting and deboning machines	7	23.3%
Blast freezing and IQF technology	6	20%
Vacuum packaging	5	16.7%
Fish smoking and drying chambers	7	23.3%
Cold chain logistics	3	10%
AI-based quality control systems	2	6.7%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.4.6: Distribution of Fish Storage Methods

Fish Storage Method	Frequency (n=30)	Percentage (%)
Refrigeration (0–4°C)	9	30%
Blast freezing (-40°C)	6	20%
Ice storage	5	16.7%
Vacuum-sealed packaging	5	16.7%
Salt curing or drying	3	10%
Live fish tanks	2	6.7%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

26.7% need access to larger markets, indicating a desire to expand their customer base. 23.3% require training in pricing and marketing strategies, which can improve profitability. FAO (2020) highlights that poor market access is a major limitation for rural women in fish processing. 36.7% of women participation in fish processing require refrigeration and cold storage, indicating a need for better preservation methods to reduce spoilage. 33.3% need efficient smoking and packaging tools, which suggests an interest in improving product quality. 30% seek modern drying techniques, highlighting the need for technology that enhances fish drying efficiency. These findings are consistent with Ahmed *et al.*, (2021), who argue that inadequate processing equipment reduces productivity and income in women-led fish businesses.

The findings reveal that 60% of women participation in fish processing use mobile phones or the internet for business purposes, showing a positive trend toward digital adoption. However, 40% of women still lack access, which aligns with GSMA (2021) findings that digital gender gaps persist due to affordability and literacy barriers. The results show that 33.3% of women participation in fish processing lack health insurance, putting them at financial risk in case of illness. 26.7% do not have maternity benefits, which may discourage long-

term participation in fish processing. ILO (2021) highlights that inadequate social protection reduces women's economic security and stability. 30% of women participation in fish processing believe financial support should be prioritized, which aligns with Ayoade and Ibrahim (2020) findings that microfinance helps women entrepreneurs expand their businesses. 26.7% suggest offering more training programs, which would improve skill development.

Strategies to promote women's participation in fish processing

The results indicate that 30% of women participation in fish processing need training in modern fish preservation techniques, highlighting the importance of proper preservation methods for reducing waste and increasing profitability. 26.7% require market access strategies, emphasizing the need for improved selling opportunities. 23.3% seek business and financial management training, which aligns with findings by FAO (2021), stating that financial literacy improves women's entrepreneurship in agribusiness. 40% of women participation in fish processing prefer microfinance loans, suggesting that access to small loans is a key barrier to growth. 33.3% favor savings programs, indicating the importance of

Table 4.4.7: Distribution of Marketing Channels Used in Fish Sales

Marketing Channels	Frequency (n=30)	Percentage (%)
Direct sales to local markets	10	33.3%
Online platforms and e-commerce	6	20%
Supplying to hotels and restaurants	5	16.7%
Exporting to international buyers	3	10%
Selling through cooperatives	4	13.3%
Partnering with seafood retailers	2	6.7%
Total	30	100%

Source: -Field Survey (2025)

financial security. Adebayo and Ogunniyi (2022) argue that cooperative finance models boost women's business sustainability.

The majority (30%) support the creation of women's participation in fish processing associations and cooperatives, which aligns with ILO (2021), stating that collective action enhances women's economic participation. 26.7% prefer leadership training, highlighting the need for skills development.

40% of women participation in fish processing require social media training, showing the growing role of digital marketing in fish sales. 33.3% need online marketing platforms, aligning with GSMA (2022), which emphasizes mobile platforms as key drivers of women's economic empowerment. 23.3% use automated filleting machines and fish smoking/drying chambers, suggesting moderate technology adoption. 16.7% use vacuum packaging, showing awareness of food preservation. FAO (2020) states that investing in cold chain logistics can significantly reduce post-harvest losses.

The most common storage method is refrigeration (30%), followed by blast freezing (20%). Salt curing (10%) and live tanks (6.7%) are less common due to infrastructure limitations. Adepoju and Alarima (2021) highlight that access to modern storage increases fish product shelf life. 33.3% rely on direct sales to local markets, showing that traditional selling methods still dominate. 20% use online platforms, aligning with the trend of digitalization in agribusiness. ILO (2021) suggests that expanding women's access to e-commerce can significantly increase profitability.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that while women are significantly involved in fish processing in Sokoto Metropolis, they encounter multiple barriers that limit their potential and profitability. Socio-cultural expectations, financial limitations, inadequate technological support, and

restricted access to markets and government programs all contribute to low productivity and marginalization of women in the sector. Despite these challenges, opportunities exist for scaling women's participation through targeted interventions such as capacity-building programs, financial support, infrastructure development, and gender-sensitive policies. Empowering women in fish processing is not only crucial for their economic independence but also essential for local economic development and food security.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

Training and Capacity Building: Organize regular training programs on modern fish preservation techniques, business management, and marketing strategies. Promote awareness about available training opportunities among women.

Improving Access to Credit and Financial Services: Establish microfinance schemes specifically targeted at women in fish processing. Facilitate cooperative savings and loan associations to enhance access to financial resources.

Enhancing Access to Technology: Provide modern fish processing equipment such as drying chambers, refrigeration units, and packaging machines at subsidized rates. Develop partnerships with private sector companies to supply technology to women's cooperatives.

Market Access Improvement: Improve transportation infrastructure to enable access to broader markets. Create digital platforms and physical marketplaces that prioritize products from women fish processors.

Promoting Women's Leadership and Decision-Making: Encourage women's participation in fish processing cooperatives and leadership positions.

Implement mentorship programs and gender-focused leadership training.

Policy Interventions: Government should increase sensitization about existing supportive policies. Introduce and enforce gender-sensitive fisheries and agriculture policies to protect and promote women's rights.

Social Protection Measures: Provide affordable health insurance packages tailored for women entrepreneurs. Offer maternity support and legal protection schemes to enhance women's participation stability.

ICT Integration: Train women in the use of mobile technology, online marketing, and digital financial services to improve their business operations. Subsidize smartphones and internet access for rural women engaged in fish processing.

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